

doi:10.5281/zenodo.18737959

Influence of Social Media Usage on Academic Performance of Students in Business Education Department in Selected Universities in Owerri Education Zone, Imo State

Ani, Charity Ngozi & Prof. N. Azih

**Department of Business Education
Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki, Nigeria**

ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to ascertain the influence of social media on the academic performance of students in business education in Universities in Owerri education zone, Imo State. Specifically, the study examined the ways WhatsApp and YouTube influence the academic performance of students in business education department. Two research questions and hypotheses guided the study. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The researcher adopted descriptive survey design for the study. The population for this study was 573 business education students of Imo State University and Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education in Owerri Education zone, Imo State. Samples of two hundred and eighty-seven (287) students were used for the study. Data were collected for this study through administration of validated questionnaire on the respondents. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha Correlation coefficient formular. The overall reliability coefficient obtained was 0.78. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze data collected whereas independent t-test statistic was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significance level. The findings of the study revealed that: WhatsApp and YouTube platforms influence the academic performance of students in Business Education Department of universities in Owerri Education Zone of Imo State. The result further showed that there was no significant difference on the mean ratings of the respondents on the influence of social media on the academic performance of students of business education department in universities in Owerri education zone. It was concluded that social media platforms have played a significant role in influencing the academic performance of students generally. It could be seen that majority of the respondents make use of WhatsApp, and YouTube. It helps the students get and send educational related information which enhances their academic performance if he/she invests his/her time in the proper areas of study. The researcher recommended among other things that students should be advised on responsible use of social media platforms to improve their academic performance and time management on social media usage be incorporated into the curriculum of tertiary institutions to regulate students' use of social media.

Keywords: Social Media, Academic Performance, Students, Business Education, Universities.

INTRODUCTION

Social media has turned the world into a global village. Social media has become one of the main channels through which people quickly and regularly interact with others electronically. Social media is a group of internet-based applications built on the ideological foundations of Web 2.0 which allows the creation and exchange of user-generated contents (Paul-Mgbeafulike, & Onyeneke 2023; Kaplan & Haentien, 2020). It enhances communication skills, social participation, commitment, and improve peer

support. It creates the opportunity to network with other members who share similar or common interests, dreams and goals.

Shrestha (2019) defined social media as a means of connection among people in which they create, share and exchange information and ideas in virtual communities and networks. According to Dominic (2021), social media are online communications that use special techniques that involve participation, sharing, conversation, collaboration and linkage. Some social media includes Twitter, Yahoo Messenger, Facebook messenger, Blackberry Messenger, WhatsApp Messenger, 2go Messenger, Skype, you-tube, Goggle talk, Google messenger, etc. These social media are used by most people to interact with old and new friends, physical or internet friends (Emordi, & Igberaharhar, 2023; Asemah & Edegoh, 2022). The world has changed rapidly by the evolution of technology. This has resulted in the use of technology as the medium to explore the wide area of knowledge. The development of social media has created communication tools to aid many methods that can be applied in learning. According to Paul-Mgbeafulike, & Onyeneke (2023), YouTube, Twitter, snapchat, WhatsApp, Instagram, Hangout, Facetime, Facebook, Messenger, Skype, Myspace, Google+ Pinterest, Telegram, Reddit, LinkedIn, Flick, WeChat, Academia.edu and TedED are major social media utilized for learning.

Learning is described by Kpolovie (2014) as the complex synergy of cognitive, effective, psychomotor, environmental; experiences and other influences for acquisition, maintenance, organization, reorganization, and enhancement of changes in behavior, knowledge, skills, values, and world views for better resolution of problems. Learning is more effective if the experience makes sense to the learner. Learning means a permanent change in behavior due to teaching and other experiences. Learning improves academic performance.

Osharive (2019) stated that academic performance plays an important role in a learner. Academic performance which is measured by examination result is the outcome of a learning process, the extent to which a learner has achieved their educational goal. Generally academic performance is measured by examinations, tests and continuous assessments, (Osharive, 2019). He went further to state that since academic performance plays an important role in the life of a student, many parents, teachers, guardians, students and well-wishers are concerned with the ways their students can excel. The emphasis on academic performance which is also prevalent worldwide has encouraged many studies about the conditions promoting it. The role of academic performance as one of the predictors of students' success and also in the aspect of academic placement in schools as well as the level of employability in an individual's career is inevitable (Ezeabi, Chibuike, & Udeh, 2019; Osharive, 2019). Academic performance, which is measured by examination results, is one of the major goals of a school, universities inclusive. Schools/universities are established with the aim of imparting knowledge and skills to those who go through them. Therefore, one of the disciplines in university through which the aforementioned objectives can be achieved is Business Education.

Business education is one of the programmes in the universities that prepare learners for career in business. According to Etonyeaku (2018), business education is an educational programme that equips an individual with electronic mail, multiplayer on-line functional and saleable skills, games, telephony and peer-to-peer knowledge, attitude and value that would enable the individual operate in the environment he finds himself. Business education involves teaching students the fundamentals of theories and processes of vocational education which is offered in business. (Chibuike, 2018). Business Education according to Soralv (2020) is a term that encompasses a number of methods used to teach students the fundamental theories and processes of business. Business Education is concerned with equipping the recipients with skills needed for employment and self-reliance. It consists of formidable force in equipping the youths with the knowledge, skills and attitudes necessary for the production of goods and services which provides better life. It is also the education that provides the individual with technical competencies that will enable the individual to attain self-realization in the field of work and in business world (Atah & Ukah, 2022).

Business education students make use of social media. In many institutions of higher learning, students no longer have time to study their books. Their time is taken up with surfing the internet and chatting on social media. Most of these students claim that social media increases their learning ability and widens

their knowledge towards information access. But it is quite true that most of these students cannot use simple spellings, instead they abbreviate every word they intend to communicate with their friends. Most of them that were able to spell correctly are now unable to spell due to over involvement in social media and social networking sites (Smart, 2019). Smart further opined that students in higher institutions use the time a teacher is teaching in the classroom to chat on social media, thereby distracting themselves from the day's lectures. The study focuses on the following social media platforms: WhatsApp, and YouTube. The choice of these platforms for the study is influenced by the fact that they are the most frequently used social media by students.

WhatsApp is social media platform. WhatsApp started in the year 2009, with the tag line "Simple, Personal, Real-time messaging". It is a mobile messaging app which allows the users to exchange messages without paying for SMS. It is a text messaging alternative which is used with the help of net connection through data plan or Wi-Fi connection. Users can send unlimited number of messages and receive messages without any restrictions. They can also form groups with their families, friends, coworkers etc. They can closely connect with their people abroad. Once we download the App all our contact list members will be our members in WhatsApp. You can also block the contact number which you don't wish to receive any message from. If you don't wish to be on a group, you can go out of that group through 'exit group'. Apart from texting, we can also send photos, videos and call through videos and voice calls, etc. WhatsApp messenger works with internet connectivity and assists its users to keep one in touch with friends, teachers and relatives in the contact list (Atah & Abang, 2020). Today WhatsApp is a very popular instant messenger service used by students. Smit (2022), in their study which observed that WhatsApp application has the potential to increase learning. It also leads to interaction between students on personal, school, and course-related topics (Cifuentes & Lents, 2010; Smit, 2012), creates a sense of belonging (Doering, Lewis, Veletsianos, and Nichols-Besel, 2008; Sweeny, 2010), eliminates social barriers (Doering, Lewis, Veletsianos, Nichols-Besel, 2008), and increases students' motivation (Plana et al., 2013). By the help of these benefits, which are also supported by the studies conducted on WhatsApp (Bouhnik & Deshen, 2019; Church & de Oliveira, 2013; Nguyen & Fussell, 2016), it is agreed that this application can be a useful tool within the scope of learning anytime and anywhere, and creates collaborative learning. Kuppuswamy and Narayan (2021), argued in their study "against the notion claiming that due to the rapid popularity of social networking sites the youths tend to distract themselves from their studies and professions" but on the contrary are developing friendly and social ties with the world that revolves around them. The work of Jain et al (2020), on analysis of Impact of social networking sites in the changing mindsets of youths on social issues elucidates that men spend more time as compared to women on social networking sites to review these social issues and yet women are very sensitive to the social issues existing in the world. Johnson (2019) examines how the WhatsApp application can affect students at the Tertiary Institutions, Ghana, in the field of academic performance. The study concluded that the WhatsApp application is necessary for easy communication between students and it is very effective due to its ability to share information and resources quickly. In the same vein, Abdulla (2017) observed in his research that social media has a positive impact on academic performance and 57% of students prefer the mobile application WhatsApp as a social media for their academic purpose.

YouTube was launched in 2005 as a site where individuals and groups could record and share their own videos with little or no cost (YouTube, 2013). The YouTube is an American online video-sharing platform. YouTube allows users to upload, view, rate, share, add to playlists, report, comment on videos, and subscribe to other users. It offers a wide variety of user-generated and corporate media videos. Available contents include video clips, TV show clips, music videos, short and documentary films, audio recordings, movie trailers, live streams, and others such as video blogging, short original videos, and educational videos. If well-utilized, the YouTube could be a veritable tool for teaching and learning process (Ochui, Agim & Atah, 2022). But many students today do not make good use of the YouTube packages.

This website (YouTube) provides business education students with authentic situations and with everyday clips that help them to get better understanding of business education concepts. The power of YouTube as

instructional package for learning depends on how it is used. However, Paul, Baker, and Cochran (2022) noted that the use of social media in education system has advantages and disadvantages. Social media sites increase student's collaborations. It provides an avenue for students to easily contact one another regarding school projects, group assignments and homework assignments, etc. Students who do not participate regularly in the classroom can express their thoughts through social media, although this should not completely replace in- class participation. It can help build the students' confidence and encourage them to find their voice and be able to participate in class. Social media sites can be useful for homework. When students have questions about a class assignment, they can easily post a message asking if anyone can help. www.windsor.edu, (2019); YouTube, (2018). Duffy, (2018), that YouTube can be utilized to distribute educational content since it enables collaborative content development and peer evaluation, which enhances the social learning experience. Additionally, the usage of video for educational purposes provides advantages over text and static visuals. Specifically, Berk (2019) stated that video technology is an effective mode of instruction because it offers students with the same materials using multimedia mode. YouTube has therefore been identified as an effective medium for supporting procedural learning (Lee and Lehto, 2020) and is a promising tool for supporting learning (Balakrishnan et al., 2015). In addition, the concept of channel subscriptions encourages active learning by notifying users when new content is added. YouTube's "Education" category contains channels connected to university courses and other forms of educational programmes. In addition, YouTube was created with viewing and updating indexes (Chelaru et al., 2014) that assist the search for video material. In conclusion, auto-captioning and translation of YouTube videos have significantly broadened their accessibility to a much larger audience (O'Neil, 2011). The research indicates that the use of YouTube by academics has attracted considerable attention. Using YouTube has also been demonstrated to improve the quality of online courses (Jones & Graham, 2013). According to Berk (2009), Logan (2012), and other sources, YouTube has proven to be an excellent aid in online tutoring classes, since it promotes independent study, enhances lectures, and aids in tutoring courses (Miller, 2009). Tan and Pearce (2011) found that incorporating YouTube videos into the learning and teaching of an introductory sociology course for senior and international students was an effective strategy for promoting student learning in delivery styles, and the use of everyday examples to teach concepts

Krasilnikov, & Smirnova (2017) noted that gender difference exists in social media usage among young students. They opined that men use it mostly for entertainment, while women use social media for communication and information purposes. They also stated that there is a clear difference between both gender about their social media usage. Making new contacts is purely attributed to men and while women used it for academic and informational aspirations. Mazman & Usluel (2016), likewise, addressing the impacts of social media on academic performance stated that with the advancement in technology, the use of social media has become rampant. Moreover, the time spent on social media sites has risen by 62.5 percent since 2012 and continues to grow. During the last year, the average time teenagers which students/learners were inclusive spent on social media was estimated at 2 - 6 hours per day.

Social media as widely argued seems to be a two-edge sword with both positive and negative sides for instance, Mowafy (2018) affirmed that the impact of social media on learning is increasingly considered and debated among higher education scholars, administrators, and stakeholders. Though, Holland and Tiggermann (2016) stated that when engaging in social media platforms, users can create highly interactive communications through which individuals, communities, and organizations can share, create, discuss, and modify user-generated content or pre-made content posted online for educational purposes. The lingering divergent views of scholars, educational administrators and stakeholders on the influence of social media on academic performance of students deserves further investigation in respect to practical-oriented courses such as business education. It is based on this background that this study was carried out to examine influence of social media usage on the academic performance of students in business education departments in universities in Owerri Education Zone, Imo State.

Statement of the Problem

The advent of smart phones and the provision of internet accessibility by network providers has increased the explosion in social media usage. The use of social media in educational system gives students the

opportunity to seek for relevant and useful information required for them to excel meaningfully in their studies and to make interactions with friends and family both within and outside the school. Social media also afford the students the avenue to connect with each other for learning activities without any requirement for physical contact. However, studies have shown that students spend most of their time on social media than they do in their studies. This phenomenon has become a source of worry to educational stakeholders especially parents. Parents and guardians are worried that their wards spend much of their study time on Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube, twitter, snapchat, among others.

One of the challenges of social media is that attention has been shifted from visible to invisible friends. Important academic activities like studying and writing might be affected in the process. Therefore, there is need to examine the influence of social media on students' academic performance in higher institutions. Academic performance of students is facing a lot of neglect and challenges. There is deviation, distraction and divided attention between social media activities and their academic work. It is observed that students devote more attention to social media than they do to their studies. It is therefore of great importance to explore some of the trending challenges facing students' academic performance as a result of social media. Students at all levels of learning now have divided attention to studies. This is due to the availability of opportunities created by social media for sundry purposes. Whether these opportunities promote studies is a question that needs to be answered. It is against this background that this study was conducted to examine the influence of social media on the academic performance of business education students in selected universities in Owerri Education Zone, Imo State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study generally was to examine the influence of social media usage on the academic performance of business education students in universities in Owerri Education Zone, Imo State. Specifically, the study sought to determine the:

1. Influence of WhatsApp on the academic performance of students of business education departments in universities in Owerri Education Zone, Imo State.
2. Influence of YouTube on the academic performance of students of business education departments in universities in Owerri Education Zone, Imo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the influence of WhatsApp on the academic performance of students in Business Education Departments in Universities in Owerri Education Zone, Imo State?
2. What is the influence of YouTube on the academic performance of students in Business Education Departments in Universities in Owerri Education Zone, Imo State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses tested at 0.05 significant level guided the study.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on the influence of WhatsApp on the academic performance of students in Business Education Departments in Universities in Owerri Education Zone, Imo State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on the influence of YouTube on the academic performance of students in Business Education Departments in Universities in Owerri Education Zone, Imo State.

RESULTS

Research Question one: *What are the ways WhatsApp influences the academic performance of students in Business Education Departments in selected Universities in Owerri Education Zone, Imo State?*
 Analysis of data related to this research question is presented in table 1.

Table 1: Mean Ratings on Influence of WhatsApp on the academic performance of students in Business Education Departments in Universities in Owerri Education Zone.

S/N	Items on ways WhatsApp Influences the academic performance of students of Business education department in selected universities in Owerri Education zone	N	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
13.	WhatsApp enables students to get study materials from one another.	230	3.16	0.81	Agree
14.	It is used by students to develop themselves intellectually.	230	2.93	0.88	Agree
15.	It is more convenient for students' use.	230	3.02	0.85	Agree
16.	WhatsApp enables the sharing of multimedia information like videos and photos which helps students to improve their study habit.	230	3.10	0.71	Agree
17.	It is user-friendly as messages are easily forwarded for wider dissemination of information.	230	3.04	0.78	Agree
18.	It reduces interpersonal relations among students.	230	3.22	0.92	Agree
19.	It negatively affects students' use of English Language.	230	3.03	0.95	Agree
20.	WhatsApp promotes collaboration in academics with other Business Education students.	230	2.86	0.79	Agree
21.	WhatsApp exposes students to watching obscene videos.	230	2.83	0.81	Agree
22.	It is used mostly by students for chatting with friends instead of doing their academic work.	230	2.61	0.96	Agree
23.	It encourages laziness among those students who rely more on information from others in doing their academic work.	230	3.10	0.71	Agree
24.	WhatsApp makes it possible for students to express their feelings using Emojis.	230	3.04	0.78	Agree
Overall mean			3.00	0.83	Agree

Table 1 presents the result of the mean ratings on the influence of WhatsApp on the academic performance of students in business education departments in Universities in Owerri Education Zone. The respondents rated all the items - 13 to 24 higher than 2.5 which is the cut off mark or basis of decision rule. The overall mean of 3.00 indicates that WhatsApp influence academic performance of students in Business Education Departments in Universities in Owerri Education Zone, Imo State. The standard deviation range of 0.71-0.96 implies that there is not much difference on respondents' opinion on WhatsApp and business education students' academic performance.

Research Question Two: *What are the ways YouTube influences the academic performance of students in Business Education Departments in selected Universities in Owerri Education Zone, Imo State?*
 Analysis of data related to this research question is presented in table 4.

Table 2: Mean ratings on Influence of YouTube on the Academic Performance of students in Business Education Departments in Universities in Owerri Education Zone.

S/N	Items on ways YouTube influences the academic performance of students in Business education departments in Owerri Education zone	N	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
25.	It allows students to upload videos for fellow students to access for use in their academic work.	230	3.00	0.82	Agree
26.	It allows students to view uploaded videos.	230	2.92	0.88	Agree
27.	YouTube enables students to rate uploaded videos.	230	3.02	0.85	Agree
28.	It allows students to comment on videos uploaded by fellow students.	230	3.10	0.71	Agree
29.	It enables students find videos that align with their preferred way of learning.	230	3.14	0.78	Agree
30.	Users subscribe to videos that align with their academic work.	230	3.24	0.93	Agree
31.	YouTube promotes students' understanding of information relating to their academic work.	230	3.16	0.93	Agree
32.	It enhances students' retention of information relating to their academic work.	230	2.90	0.81	Agree
33.	YouTube shares videos that attract the attention of students.	230	2.93	0.83	Agree
34.	YouTube offers videos that develop students' mentality.	230	2.84	0.78	Agree
35.	It shares videos that enhance students' creativity.	230	3.10	0.71	Agree
36.	YouTube offers flexibility to students as they can access academic videos at any time allowing them to learn at their own pace and convenience.	230	3.04	0.78	Agree
37.	It enables students gain global access to study materials.	230	3.02	0.82	Agree
38.	YouTube offers interactive learning opportunities to students which enhance their learning experiences.	230	2.92	0.88	Agree
39.	Can make student addicted to watching entertainment videos instead of educational videos.	230	3.02	0.85	Agree
40.	It can be a source of distraction to students.	230	3.23	0.72	Agree
	Overall mean		3.03	0.83	Agree

Result of the respondents' opinions on table 2 on influence of YouTube on the academic performance of students in business education departments in universities in Owerri Education Zone. The table indicates that the respondents rated items 25-40 above 2.5 which is the cut off mark or basis for decision rule. The overall mean shows 3.03 which implies that all the respondents agreed that YouTube has influence on the academic performance of students in business education departments in universities in Owerri Education zone. The standard deviation range 0.71-0.93 implies that the respondents are not different in their opinions on YouTube and business education academic performance.

Test of Hypotheses

Three null hypotheses were tested in this section. The t-test statistics was used for analyzing data relating to the three hypotheses. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significant level.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female respondents on ways WhatsApp influences the academic performance of students in business education departments in selected universities in Owerri education zone in Imo State. To test the hypothesis, the independent t-test values of

the two groups (male and female students) were computed at 0.05 significant level. The result of the computation is shown in table 3 below:

Table 3: Independent t-test analysis of male and female students' mean ratings on ways WhatsApp influences the academic performance of students in business education department in selected universities in Owerri education zone.

S/N	Items	Gender	N	\bar{x}	SD	Df	t-cal	p-value	Remark	Dec
13.	WhatsApp enables students to get study materials from one another.	Male	96	3.11	.869	228	-.297	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	3.15	.880					
14.	It is used by students to develop themselves intellectually.	Male	96	3.13	.824	228	-1.009	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	3.23	.735					
15.	It is more convenient for students' use.	Male	96	3.14	.790	228	1.200	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	3.01	.809					
16.	WhatsApp enables the sharing of multimedia information like videos and photos which helps students to improve their study habit.	Male	96	3.07	.837	228	1.771	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	2.87	.853					
17.	It is user-friendly as messages are easily forwarded for wider dissemination of information.	Male	96	2.97	.945	228	1.914	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	2.73	.902					
18.	It reduces interpersonal relations among students.	Male	96	3.01	.864	228	1.610	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	2.83	.818					
19.	negatively affects students' use of English Language.	Male	96	2.94	.831	228	..954	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	2.83	.889					
20.	Whatsapp promotes collaboration in academics with other Business Education students.	Male	96	3.09	.859	228	2.049	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	2.86	.860					
21.	Whatsapp exposes students to watching obscene videos.	Male	96	2.92	.948	228	.447	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	2.86	1.020					
22.	It is used mostly by students for chatting with friends instead of doing their academic work.	Male	96	2.95	.851	228	-.788	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	3.04	.844					
23.	It encourages laziness among those students who rely more on information from others in doing their academic work.	Male	96	3.28	.721	228	1.074	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	3.17	.818					
24.	WhatsApp makes it possible for students to express their feelings using Emojis.	Male	96	3.03	.945	228	1.596	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	2.82	1.039					

*NS= Not Significant (P< 1.96) at 0.05 level,

An independent t-test was conducted to compare the differences in the mean ratings of male and female students on ways WhatsApp influences the academic performance of students of business education department in selected universities in Owerri education zone in Imo State. Table 3 indicates the obtained t-value which showed that items 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 22, 23and 24 respectively were all

accepted the respondents. These values were tested for significant by comparing them with the critical value of (1.96) at 0.05 significant level with 228 degrees of freedom. The obtained t-values were less than the critical (1.96). Hence, the results were not significant and the null hypothesis was accepted. The result therefore means that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female students on ways WhatsApp influences the academic performance of students in business education department in universities in Owerri education zone in Imo State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female respondents on the ways YouTube influences the academic performance of students of business education department in universities in Owerri education zone in Imo State. To test the third hypothesis, the independent t-test values of the two groups (male and female students) were computed at 0.05 significant level. The result of the computation is shown in table 4 below:

Table 4: Independent t-test analysis of male and female students’ mean ratings on ways YouTube influences the academic performance of students in business education department in universities in Owerri Education Zone.

S/N	Items	Gender	N	\bar{x}	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Remark	Dec
25.	It allows students to upload videos for fellow students to access for use in their academic work.	Male	96	2.84	.825	228	-.297	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	2.96	.730					
26.	It allows students to view uploaded videos.	Male	96	2.91	.834	228	-1.009	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	2.91	.780					
27.	YouTube enables students to rate uploaded videos.	Male	96	3.25	.781	228	1.200	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	3.16	.857					
28.	It allows students to comment on videos uploaded by fellow students.	Male	96	3.15	.858	228	1.771	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	3.17	.809					
29.	It enables students find videos that align with their preferred way of learning.	Male	96	3.16	.744	228	1.914	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	3.05	.744					
30.	Users subscribe to videos that align with their academic work.	Male	96	3.13	.798	228	1.610	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	2.96	.812					
31.	YouTube promotes students’ understanding of information relating to their academic work.	Male	96	3.04	.893	228	.954	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	2.95	.976					
32.	It enhances students’ retention of information relating to their academic work.	Male	96	3.00	.846	228	2.049	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	2.99	.888					
33.	YouTube shares videos that attract the attention of students.	Male	96	2.93	.824	228	.447	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	2.79	.893					
34.	YouTube offers videos that develop students’ mentality.	Male	96	2.98	.882	228	-.788	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	3.01	.832					
35.	It shares videos that enhance students’ creativity.	Male	96	2.91	.859	228	1.074	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	2.66	1.069					

36.	YouTube offers flexibility to students as they can access academic videos at any time allowing them to learn at their own pace and convenience.	Male	96	3.01	.801	228	1.596	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	3.01	.756					
37.	It enables students gain global access to study materials.	Male	96	3.34	.792	228	1.901	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	3.22	.921					
38.	YouTube offers interactive learning opportunities to students which enhance their learning experiences.	Males	96	2.93	1.059	228	-.043	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	2.72	1.115					
39.	It can be a source of distraction to students.	Male	96	3.34	.834	228	1.123	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	3.22	.780					
40.	YouTube can make a student become addicted to watching entertainment videos instead of educational videos.	Male	96	2.91	.792	228	1.456	1.96	Agree	NS
		Female	134	2.91	.921					

*NS= Not Significant P<1.96 at 0.05 level,

An independent t-test was conducted to compare the differences in the mean ratings of male and female students on ways YouTube influences the academic performance of students of business education department in universities in Owerri education zone in Imo State. Table 4 presents the obtained t-value which showed that items 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39 and 40 respectively were all accepted the respondents. These values were tested for significant by comparing them with the critical value of (1.96) at 0.05 significant level with 228 degrees of freedom. The obtained t-values were less than the critical (1.96). Hence, the results were not significant and the null hypothesis was accepted. Therefore, the result means that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female students on ways YouTube influences the academic performance of students of business education department in universities in Owerri education zone in Imo State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result of analysis of data revealed that the respondents accepted all items on ways WhatsApp influences the academic performance of students in business education. They agreed that WhatsApp enables students to get study materials from one another, is used by students to develop themselves intellectually and more convenient for students' use. They also agreed that WhatsApp enables the sharing of multimedia information like videos and photos which helps students to improve their study habit, that it is user-friendly as messages are easily forwarded for wider dissemination of information, and reduces certain inconveniences among students WhatsApp, they agreed promotes collaboration in academics among Business Education students but it could encourage laziness among those students who rely more on information from others in doing their academic work. This opinion is supported by Smit (2022), in their study which observed that WhatsApp application has the potential to increase learning. It also leads to interaction between students on personal, school, and course-related topics (Cifuentes & Lents, 2010; Smit, 2012), creates a sense of belonging (Doering, Lewis, Veletsianos, and Nichols-Besel, 2008; Sweeny, 2010), eliminates social barriers (Doering, Lewis, Veletsianos, Nichols-Besel, 2008), and increases students' motivation (Plana et al., 2013). By the help of these benefits, which are also supported by the studies conducted on WhatsApp (Bouhnik & Deshen, 2019; Church & de Oliveira, 2013; Nguyen & Fussell, 2016), it is agreed that this application can be a useful tool within the scope of learning anytime and anywhere, and creates collaborative learning. Kuppuswamy and Narayan (2021), argued in their study "against the notion claiming that due to the rapid popularity of social networking sites the

youths tend to distract themselves from their studies and professions” but on the contrary are developing friendly and social ties with the world that revolves around them. The work of Jain et al (2020), on analysis of Impact of social networking sites in the changing mindsets of youths on social issues elucidates that men spend more time as compared to women on social networking sites to review these social issues and yet women are very sensitive to the social issues existing in the world. Johnson (2019) examines how the WhatsApp application can affect students at the Tertiary Institutions, Ghana, in the field of academic performance. The study concluded that the WhatsApp application is necessary for easy communication between students and it is very effective due to its ability to share information and resources quickly. In the same vein, Abdulla (2017) observed in his research that social media has a positive impact on academic performance and 57% of students prefer the mobile application WhatsApp as a social media for their academic purpose.

The result of the analysis of the data showed that the respondents agreed that YouTube influences the academic performance of students in business education department in such ways as allowing them to upload videos for fellow students to access for use in their academic work. It allows students to view uploaded videos, rate the uploaded videos and comment on them. It enables students find videos that align with their preferred way of learning. YouTube promotes students’ understanding of information relating to their academic work and enhances students’ retention of information relating to their academic work. Overall, the items were rated higher than the cut off by the respondents. The opinion of the respondents aligns with the view of Duffy, (2018), that YouTube can be utilized to distribute educational content since it enables collaborative content development and peer evaluation, which enhances the social learning experience. Additionally, the usage of video for educational purposes provides advantages over text and static visuals. Specifically, Berk (2019) stated that video technology is an effective mode of instruction because it offers students with the same materials using multimedia mode. YouTube has therefore been identified as an effective medium for supporting procedural learning (Lee and Lehto, 2020) and is a promising tool for supporting learning (Balakrishnan et al., 2015). In addition, the concept of channel subscriptions encourages active learning by notifying users when new content is added. YouTube’s “Education” category contains channels connected to university courses and other forms of educational programmes. In addition, YouTube was created with viewing and updating indexes (Chelaru et al., 2014) that assist the search for video material. In conclusion, auto-captioning and translation of YouTube videos have significantly broadened their accessibility to a much larger audience (O’Neil, 2011). The research indicates that the use of YouTube by academics has attracted considerable attention. Using YouTube has also been demonstrated to improve the quality of online courses (Jones & Graham, 2013). According to Berk (2009), Logan (2012), and other sources, YouTube has proven to be an excellent aid in online tutoring classes, since it promotes independent study, enhances lectures, and aids in tutoring courses (Miller, 2009). Tan and Pearce (2011) found that incorporating YouTube videos into the learning and teaching of an introductory sociology course for senior and international students was an effective strategy for promoting student learning in delivery styles, and the use of everyday examples to teach concepts.

CONCLUSION

From the outcome of the study, it was concluded that social media platforms have played significant roles in influencing the academic performance of students generally. It could be seen that majority of the respondents make use of WhatsApp, Facebook and YouTube. It helps the students get and send educational related information which enhances their academic performance if they invest their time in the proper areas of studies. The study also discovered that some of the features of social media such as recording, audio/video calls and texts have really contributed so much in information dissemination for students. Students get to easily know about emergency activities, programmes, classes and other relevant information. Absentee students also take advantage of these platforms to get information.

The research shows that social media has really played an effective role in influencing the academic performance of students in business education department of universities in Owerri education zone.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher made the following recommendations:

1. Students should be enlightened on the effects of resorting to short forms in their spellings and grammatical construction of sentences during communication on WhatsApp as this may affect them in real situation thereby affecting their academic performance.
2. For students to get maximum benefits from social media, they should be encouraged to join educational groups in order to learn from one another, devote more time to studying and less to chatting. They should be encouraged to only log in online and chat at leisure times to avoid time wastage.

REFERENCES

- Abdulla. A. S. (2017). Social media and its influence on students' performance. *Jamb News* 3(21), 4-5.
- Asemah, E. S. & Edegoh, L. O. N. (2022). Influence of Social Media on the Academic Performance of the Undergraduate Students of Kogi State University, Anyigba, Nigeria. *Journal of Research on Humanities and Social Sciences* 3(12).
- Atah, C. A. & Abang, M. B. (2020). Influence of WhatsApp applications software on academic performance of business education students in federal college of education Obudu. *World Journal of Innovation and Modern Technology*, 5(1), 40-49.
- Atah, C. A. & Ukah, T. A. (2022). Influence of social media utilization and academic rendition of business education students in university of Cross River State (UNICROSS), Nigeria. *Academic Journal of Current Research*, 9(1), 17 - 22.
- Balakrishnan, M, A. L., Nuaimi, A., Guang, Y. A.L., & Rashedi, A. (2015). Analysis of gender differences in academic self-efficacy and achievement among secondary school students in Niger state, Nigeria. *International journal of social sciences*, 5(3), 155-164. <https://doi.org/10.20319/pijss.2020.53.6596>
- Berk, K. (2009). The influence of social networks on high school students' performance. *International Journal of Web-Based Learning and Teaching Technologies*, 10(2), 49-59.
- Berk, S. L. (2019). YouTube impact on the academic performance of students from a village in India. *International journal of research and analytical reviews (IJRAR.ORG)*
- Bouhnik, K. & Deshen, R. (2019). The impact of social media on student academic life in higher education. *Global Journal of Human-Social Science*, 16(4), 1-8
- Chelaru, W. L. (2014). *Secrets of Online and Multimedia Journalism: A manual for online and Multimedia Journalism Practice in Africa*. Ibadan: Emgee Publishers Ltd.
- Chibuike, A. C. (2018). *Secrets of Online and Multimedia Journalism: A manual for online and Multimedia Journalism Practice in Africa*. Ibadan: Emgee Publishers Ltd.
- Church, D. & de Oliveira, W. (2013). Impact of YouTube educational tutorials on the academic performance of intermediate students of Lahore *journal of media and educational science* (2020 doi 10.56536}
- Cifuentes & Lents, (2010). The Need for Safety Consciousness Among Youths on Social Media Networking Sites. *Journal of Applied Science and Management (JASM)*, 14(1). 34-42
- Dominic, K. (2021). The use of social media among students of mass communication. *Journal of distance Education* 17(2), 83-95.
- Duffy, P. (2018). A study on impact of social media on educational efforts in Guwahati City, Assam. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Education Technology*, 2(3), 90-94
- Emordi, J. E. & Igberaharhar, O. C. (2023). Influence of social media platforms on academic performance of business education students in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta State - Nigeria. *International Journal of Research*, 10(12)
- Etoneyaku, A. S (2018). Students' social media use and its perceived impact on their social life: a case study of the University of Zambia. *The International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research* 1-15.

- Ezeabi, I. C., Chibuike, V. C. & Udeh, S. O. (2019). Influence of social media on academic performance of business education students in public universities in South East of Nigeria. *European Centre for Research Training and Development*, 7(2), 81 - 90.
- Holland and Tiggermann (2016). The Influence of Social networks on Students' Academic Performance. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Computing and Information Sciences*, 5(12)23-26.
- Jain et al (2020). Investigating instructional strategies for using social media in formal and informal learning. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 13(1), 87-104
- Johnson, G. (2019). Online content creation: Looking at students' social media practices through a connected learning lens. *Learning, Media and Technology*, 41(1), 140-159.
- Jones, J. & Graham, D. (2013). In online and campus-based career and technical education (CTE) courses. *Community College Journal of Research and Practice*, 29, 369–394
- Kaplan, A. M. & Haenlein, M., (2020). Users of the World, Unite: The Challenges and Opportunities of Social Media. *Business Horizons Journal*, 53(1) 59-68.
- Kpolovie, R (2014). The effect of Twitter on college student engagement and grades, *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 2010
- Krasilnikov, R. & Smirnova, K. (2017). Facebook addiction among Malaysian students. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 6(6), 82-90
- Kuppuswamy, M. & Narayan, D. (2021). Effect of social media on academic performance of students in Ghanaian universities: A study of university of Ghana, Legon. Retrieved from <https://www.google.com/u>
- Lee, W. & Lehto, E. K. (2020). *Test, measurement and evaluation in education*. (2nd ed), Owerri: spring Publishers Limited
- Logan, D. (2012). Social Media & Mobile Internet Use among Teens and Young Adults. *Pew Research Center's Internet & American Life Project*. Retrieved from [http://web.pewinternet.org/~media/Files/Reports/2010/PIP social media and Young Adults Report Final with toplines.pdf](http://web.pewinternet.org/~media/Files/Reports/2010/PIP_social_media_and_Young_Adults_Report_Final_with_toplines.pdf)
- Mazman, G. & Usluel, Y. K. (2016). Gender differences in using social networks *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, volume 10 (2), 133-139
- Miller, G. (2009). Social media network participation and academic performance in senior high schools in Ghana. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1, 14-20.
- Mowafy, G.A.M. (2018). The effect of social media on academic performance of Nile University students: *Doctoral dissertation American University in Cairo*.
- Nguyen, K. & Fussell, W. (2016). Internet addiction and excessive social networks use: what about Facebook? *Clinical practice and epidemiology in mental health: CP & EMH*, 12, p. 43.
- O'Neil, 2011).
- Ochui, M. O., Agim, V. U. & Atah, C. A (2022). Influence of email and YouTube platform utilization on academic performance of business education students in university of Cross river State. *Academic journal of Current Research*, 9(2), 72 - 76.
- Osharive, P. (2019). Social media and academic performance of students at the university of Lagos. *Unpublished M.Ed Thesis University of Lagos*.
- Paul, J. A., Baker, H. M., & Cochran, J. D. (2022). Effect of online social networking on student academic performance. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 28,(5) 2117-
- Paul-Mgbeafulike, V. S. & Onyeneke, E. N. (2023). Social media platforms and academic excellence of office technology and management (OTM) students in South-Eastern Nigeria polytechnics. *Association of Business Educators of Nigeria Conference Proceedings*, 10(1), 507 - 515
- Plana et al., (2013). The Influence of Social Networking Sites on Students' Academic Performance in Malaysia. Retrieved from <http://utechacademic.edu> .shanlee brown.
- Shrestha, L. (2019). The impact of social media on youth: A case study of Bahawalpurcity. Pakistan and faculty of media communication, middle East University, Amman, Jordan.

- Smart, R. (2019). Perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness of social media for e-Learning in Libyan Higher Education: a Structural Equation Modeling Analysis. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 6(3): 2016.192-199.
- Smit, E. (2012). Effect of social media on undergraduate students' achievement and interest in chemistry in the Northcentral geo-political zone of Nigeria. *International Journal of Science and Technology Educational Research* 10(2): 9-15.
- Smit, H. (2022). Perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness of social media for e-Learning in Libyan Higher Education: a Structural Equation Modeling Analysis. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 6(3): 2016.192-199.
- Soralv, S. (2020). Use of social media by college students: Relationship to communication and self-concept. *Journal of Technology Research*, 4(1), 37-49.
- Tan, L. & Pearce (2011). The use of WhatsApp as an educational communication tool in higher education experience of nursing students in Kavango east. *Namibia international Journal of Higher Education* 9, 105-114